

Build a Nucleus in the Classroom with a simulation Program

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Abstract

This paper presents the study of nucleons of chemical elements with a simulation program and the creation of different chemical elements. Students in the first high school class took part in this experiment in the chemistry lesson.

For the experiment we used the University of Colorado simulation program. We created atoms by placing protons and neutrons in the nucleus studying the atomic and mass number and the half-life.

The atomic and mass number and their relationship were studied in every element we created with the Simulation program. We were able to observe on the working screen the size of the atom in relation to the nuclear particle we have placed in the nucleus and calculating the number of electrons around the nucleus in the atom. Adding neutrons and protons we were able to change the mass and atomic number. With this simulation experiment, students learn how the size of the nucleus changed with the number of protons. We were able to identify different Chemical elements according to the number of protons and neutrons of the nucleus of the element we created according to the mass and atomic number.

The main goal of the experimentation laboratory was to create new elements by integrating neutrons and protons into the nucleus. Students were able to understand the difference that the nuclei of elements show in relation to the number of protons and neutrons and understand the use of mass and atomic number as a key in to identifying chemical elements.

Key words : Protons, Neutrons, Atom, Chemical element

Introduction

The nucleus of an atom is a small, a very dense, and a round region which located in to the centre of an atom. It has two subatomic particles which are the protons and the neutrons. Protons are electrically positively charged ions having a mass of approximately one atomic mass unit (*amu*). So we say tht the mass of an atom is the mass of the nucleus. Neutrons are electrically neutral.

This nucleus of every chemical element , which is made up of protons and neutrons, contains the majority of the atom's mass (except for common hydrogen which has only one proton).

The Protons

A proton is a subatomic particle of the nucleus with a positive electric charge. They are in the nucleus of every atom of a chemical element. Protons determine the atomic number of each

chemical element. This number is also equal to the number of atomic electrons of the chemical element

and also determines the chemical properties of the element.

Protons have slightly less mass than neutrons but they have a much greater mass equal to 1,836 times that of electrons. So we can confidently say that all the mass of an atom of an element is concentrated in the nucleus. Protons and neutrons together are called nucleons in each element.

The name for "proton" comes from the Greek word meaning "first". Ernest Rutherford was the Physicist who dealt with the atoms of the elements and coined the term "proton" for the nucleus of the hydrogen atom in the year 1920.

The Neutrons

Neutrons are subatomic particles found inside the nucleus of every atom. Neutrons do not exist in the hydrogen atom whose nucleus contains a proton. Neutrons are electrically neutral, meaning they are not charged and have a mass that is slightly larger than a proton.

When neutrons are in the nucleus they are stable. But this does not happen when they are free outside the nucleus, then the neutrons have an average lifetime of about 1,000 seconds.

Neutrons, along with protons and electrons, make up the three basic particles found inside an atom. We know today that there are many more particles very important to the structure of the nucleus of the atom of each element. While protons carry a positive charge and electrons a negative charge, neutrons have no charge at all and could be said to be something like balancers (Simopoulou P. D.2008).

Isotopes are the atoms of the same chemical element which differ only in the number of neutrons so they have the same Z and different N and A. This was an important step of study and in the experiment we did with the simulation program in the laboratory. For example, carbon-12 contains 6 neutrons, while carbon-13 contains 7. James Chadwick discovered neutrons in 1932. That is, the nucleus contains 99.97279% of the total mass of the atom of the element. But the nucleus of the atom is so very small that if we magnified it by a trillion times it would be the size of the head of a pin.

So we can say that at about this magnification the electrons would orbit the nucleus at a distance that was a few meters. This means that the atom of an element as a whole in space could be the size of a fairly large room. (Simopoulos D. 2008).

Preparation

Before starting the experiment, the students studied the corresponding textbook theory related to the presentation of the atomic and mass number and to the creation of the atoms of the elements as they appear in the periodic table of the elements. The relationship between mass and atomic number and the significance of these numbers for chemical elements was analyzed.

The students understood the importance of the numbers A, Z, N to determine the position of the elements in the periodic table and their properties. (Drougas V. 2021)

The program <https://phet.colorado.edu/> of the University of Colorado was used and the build-a-nucleus chemistry simulation program was chosen, which is provided free of charge and can be used by students from the computer lab. In the particular experiment we used the interactive whiteboard in the physics and chemistry laboratory of the school.

Emphasis was placed on understanding the ratio of protons and the number of electrons the atom of each element contains in its neutral state. Thus, a greater number of protons in the nucleus mean a greater number of electrons in the atom, so the atom will present a different number of layers and its atomic distance from the center of the nucleus will increase. (Drougas V. 2022)

This cannot be easily understood from the textbook presentation of it and we chose to use the proton and neutron nucleation simulation program to make the students aware of the importance of the number of protons and neutrons in the nucleus of the atoms of the elements.

The experiment

As mentioned in the introduction we used the simulation program of the University of Colorado in the United States. From the program we chose simulation in Chemistry and build-a-nucleus. With this option, students have the possibility to choose from the work screen to place neutrons and protons in the nucleus. Attention was given to the students noticing that the nucleus does not have the ability to take only neutrons or only protons except in the case of the Hydrogen atom. It was also observed that for a certain number of neutrons we can have a certain higher number of protons in the nucleus. (Spartali N. 2010). The number of protons will give us the number of electrons spinning in shells around the nucleus. Students are able to observe the corresponding cloud created by the movement of electrons around the nucleus, as shown in the following images resulting from the experiment.

At the same time, on the right of the screen, every time they place a certain number of neutrons or protons in the nucleus, they observe the change in the name of the element and the number A, Z which represents the identity of the chemical element they have created with the new nucleus. So students can relate the theory and meaning of the numbers A and Z and the relationship to the name and identity of the element. At the same time they can understand through the representation of the electron cloud the difference in the weight of the atom and the size and detect the different behavior of the elements in Chemistry.

Students also studied Decay b and observed the change in the nucleus of the element and thus the element itself

Examples from the classroom experiment are shown below.

Typical simulation results

The following photos show images of the simulation the students made in the program and key features of the simulation on the work screen.

The experiment of simulating the creation of atoms of elements from the nucleus was a teaching hour. In the next class the students answered questions related to the experiment related to the presentation of the theory as it is presented in the textbook of the first high school.

Hydrogen - 1

Protons:	1
Neutrons:	0

Symbol
1 H 1

Helium - 4

Protons:	2
Neutrons:	2

Symbol
4 He 2

Beryllium - 6

Protons:	4
Neutrons:	2

Symbol
6 Be 4

The representation of the layer model by simulation

Feedback

After the end of the experiment the students understanding the importance of the subatomic particles of the nucleus and the role of protons and electrons in the creation of the elements and their properties could have formed an important insight into the theory of the subatomic nucleus.

Explain how the changing the number of neutrons or protons affects the atomic number and isotope species.

Describe how different decays will change the nucleons in the nucleus and if that changes the symbol of the atom being shown and affects parameters like atomic number/atomic mass.

Predict the shell model depiction of an isotope based on the isotope symbol or name.

Find the isotope on the nuclide chart using the symbol, name, or the number of protons and neutrons.

Predict the outcome

Conclusions

With the experiment of simulating the creation of atoms of the chemical elements and the difference in their naming in relation to the number of protons and neutrons of the nucleus, students were able to understand the importance of atomic and mass number in chemistry.

These numbers are very important to the identity of the chemical elements and their place in the periodic table.

The simulation program allowed the students to very easily experiment with creating chemical elements by changing the structure of the nucleus and observing how new elements are created. They were very easily able to relate the theoretical presentation of the textbook and understand the role of the nucleus in the creation of chemical elements.

It was also understood the position of protons and neutrons in the atom and their relationship with the electrons of a neutral atom as well as the relationship of the energy layers of the atoms of the elements based on the electronic structure and the energy positions of the electrons K,L,M,N... Relevant experiments in the school curriculum in the chemistry lesson can help students understand the essence of chemistry and the role of chemical elements in relation to their structure.

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